

THE CONTENT AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF TEACHING NATIONAL VALUES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Abdurashidov Adhamjon Abdulhamitovich

Associate professor of Kokand state pedagogical university, philosophy doctor (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7833971>

Abstract. *In this article the main components of Uzbek national values and traditions and their role in the upbringing of preschool children have been analyzed from a scientific and theoretical point of view. The intensive ways of folk pedagogy in teaching Uzbek national values and traditions to preschool children have also been discussed.*

Keywords: *preschool education, national values, upbringing, family, society, reform, politics, event, heritage, spirituality.*

The sustainable progress and development of every country depends on the human factor, in particular, on the scientific, creative and spiritual potential of the young generation. Today, the problems of youth education are a common issue for almost all countries. The age-old traditions of the Uzbek people, including traditions in the field of education, are connected with the blessing religion of our ancestors. Traditions such as greeting the elderly, respecting them, caring for the young and weak, will for learning and get a profession, hardworking, and being polite to neighbors are common in Uzbek families, inculcated in young people regardless of their attitude to religion. Development of national forms of interests and abilities of preschool children is one of the important tasks of preschool education. The communication between children of preschool education and their tutor should be based on the specific goal taking into account interests and abilities, spiritual resources, the requirements and needs of the present time.

It is necessary to understand its essence of “human” in raising children of preschool age based on universal human values. Values are divided into several types according to their nature. In particular, a person and his life are the highest value. It is absurd to talk about the value of something in the absence of a human itself. That is why honoring human dignity, improving his life, developing his knowledge and cultural level, maintaining his health, and protecting his life are the main directions of our state's policy. All of the fundamental changes and reforms taking place in our society make people's lives full, rich, beautiful, people feel truly free, the results of their work, their destiny, and made them feel of possessing to this country.

The activities of our educators in pre-school educational organizations to make our young generations understand the interests of the country, nation and the Motherland, to further increase their fame, to study science and culture, the rich heritage, history, religion and values of our ancestors, and to evaluate them appropriately are very important. The essential way of teaching is showing a video about the life and creative path of scientists, writers and poets on the theme of harmony of nationality and national spiritual values in the organization of preschool education in educating preschool children on the basis of national values, effectively instilling national-spiritual, ethnic values into the minds of young people.

National values are not some immutable phenomena. Improvement of social, economic, and spiritual life related to the development of the nation, changes in living and working conditions

make it possible for national values to develop as well. Educating children of preschool age on the basis of universal values requires thinking, deep knowledge and specialization from the young generation based on the national idea. Its basis is our national values. The feeling of living in a new way, building a free and prosperous Motherland, free and prosperous life, puts more responsible tasks before the younger generation. In particular, the fact that changes in consciousness, thinking and spiritual values lag behind the demands of modern life is related to defects in spiritual potential.

In order to educate the children in the pre-school education establishments based on our national values, it is appropriate to start slowly introducing them to the local environment. The main goals and tasks of educating children of preschool age are to develop children mentally and physically, to ensure the development of their psyche, personal abilities, aspirations and needs, national and universal values, taking into account regional characteristics prepare them for school education.

It is desirable to bring up preschool children on the basis of universal human values, the possibilities of our blessed religion in educational and cultural education, and the use of our great spiritual and educational heritage to the level of the first issue. During training, it is necessary to give examples of Uzbek folk proverbs to students, to memorize them, and to convey our stories and tales in an easy and comprehensible way. If holidays and events are organized on the basis of our national values, including Uzbek national costumes, songs will be remembered in the child's mind in a positive way.

Today, in preschool education organizations, serious work is being done on the implementation of the concept of improvement of the preschool education system until 2030, approved by the President. Among them, there is creating of didactic materials aimed at educating children in the spirit of national values in preschool educational organizations. As well as, many of these materials are modernized materials prepared in the Soviet era or Russian folk tales, proverbs and pictures adapted to them, and didactic materials aimed at educating the students of preschool educational organizations in the spirit of national values are extremely relevant.

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan developed an approach to this topic based on universal principles. The emergence of such a view, the social and spiritual renewal of values, the maturity of society members and the importance of education of young people at the state level, is the main direction of the development of this field. Positive processes of appreciation of values as one of the moral factors of strengthening independence require increasing research and increasing responsibility for them. Independence put on the agenda to restore the issues and standards of Uzbek appreciation and improve them to the level of modern requirements. After all, the value system of a non-independent country will never be complete. It is clear that the values of the colonizers take priority in the spiritual life of the colonial country. Only independence will fundamentally change this situation, make the country's value complex an equal and real part of the world system. For this reason, independence required the formation of a new system of values. This necessity is combined with the process of re-evaluating values and forming a way of life in our country, in which eastern, ancient and universal criteria of appreciation are the priority. This is the reason why there is a growing need to pay attention to changes in the field of values and to use new principles in this regard in education. There are sayings of our people: "Without value, there is no value!", "Unappreciated value is like a mirage." That's why we should highly value

such values as independence, great future, patriotism, humanitarianism, democracy, and the rule of law, which are the highest expressions of the development of our country.

The process of teaching in preschool education organizations should be organized on the basis of various didactic materials to educate children in the spirit of national values. In this regard, we give the following recommendations: The first didactic material is devoted to the topic "Father-mind, mother-cognition", and this didactic material is intended for a group of six-year-old children. The training will be held in the group room. The training lasts 20 minutes. The training is carried out in the form of text reading, narration, interaction, theatrical presentation, speech. The training is carried out by video and audio means. During the training, children are rewarded with applause and toys. We usually call the father a bad father, and a mother a kind mother, which is used many times in the everyday meaning and essence of this proverb. Because there is no person greater and dearer than father, kinder and closer than mother for every person. Indeed, parents are great beings. Together with you, they brought us into the world, they take care of us like the apple of their eye, they not only bring us to adulthood, but they are always like the sun shining light on our life, and they illuminate our night like the moon. For this reason, it is not for nothing that the most beautiful epics, the best songs, and the sweetest melodies are dedicated to these great people. The above-mentioned concepts are taught to children in preschool education organizations through songs, fairy tales, proverbs, and wise words.

In the traditions of the Uzbek people is emphasized the etiquette that comes from history, it is importance of upbringing the child in a spirit of fights for the good of the country, who thinks not of himself, but of the happiness of people, and who realizes the unfulfilled dreams of the generations.

We must educate the future generation in pre-school education organizations based on national values in the spirit of respect for parents, respect for teachers, loyalty to the people, and boundless love for the motherland. In this regard, it is appropriate to inculcate these values in the minds of children by organizing spiritual-educational activities in preschool educational organizations in every lesson, through proverbs, tales, poems from folk art. Teaching the basics of modern value science, which is a complex of knowledge about the sense of value and appreciation, the category of values, their essence, and the forms of their content, in the education and formation of preschoolers as representatives of a spiritually mature generation. extremely important. It is for this reason that one of the main criteria of the effectiveness of education is to use the opportunity of generalizing the achievements of humanity in terms of standards of appreciation. In raising preschool children on the basis of universal human values, the first and most common of values is life itself, because the loss of life destroys the use of all other values. Other types of values are, in essence, the essence of life's blessings, cultural values.

REFERENCES

1. Azizova Z. Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda qo‘g‘irchoq teatri vositasida axloqiy-estetik sifatlarni shakllantirish. – T., 2010.
2. Boboyeva D.R. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning nutqini o‘stirish jarayonida ertaklar asosida atrof-muhit bilan tanishtirish //Ilmiy to‘plam. – T.: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU. 2000. – 103-105-b.
3. Jabborova S.Z. Osobennosti truda v doshkolnom vozraste // problemi pedagogiki. – 2020 .

4. Kamilova G. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ekologik tarbiyani tashkil etishda integrativ yondashuv //centr nauchnix publikaciy (buxdu. uz). – 2020.
5. Abdurashidov A.A. O'quvchi-yoshlarda tadbirkorlik tushunchalarini shakllantirishning muhim belgilari // Uzluksiz ta'lim – Tashkent , 2019. – №2. – B.87-89. (13.00.00; №9)
6. Abdurashidov A.A. Milliy hunarmandchilik vositasida talabalarda tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish // Pedagogika jurnali – Tashkent, 2019. – №4. – B.68-73.
7. Abdurashidov A.A. Methodology of formation skills of entrepreneurship among students through the national crafts // European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences – Great Britain, 2019. – Volume 7 Number 7. P.41-45.
8. Abdurashidov A.A. Vospitanie samostoyatl'nosti u studentov v Vuze kak effektivnaya forma podgotovki visokokvalificirovannih kadrov// Problem of modern education: V international scientific conference. – Tashkent, 2014. – B.3.